

ISic0214

I.Sicily inscription 0214

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano, inventory 58

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Ex] d(ecreto) d(ecurionum)
2. [L(ucio)] Rufeio L(uci) f(ilio) Qui(rina tribu)
3. Laeto
4. in front(e) · p(edes) · XXV
5. in agr(o) · p(edes) · XXX

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini and photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175695

EDR 077914

EDCS 8900392

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1980.0514

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 138

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